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Ultrasound transducers with an optical window

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Ultrasound is one of the most cost-effective deep tissue clinical imaging modalities. Near all ultrasound transducers are fabricated from piezoelectric materials that require metal surface electrodes, making the transducers opaque. With the increasing need for multi-modal and compact imaging and therapeutic tools new transducers fabrication techniques need to be evaluated. In our work we evaluate several designs that allow a large optical window in combination with ultrasonic propagation collinear to the imaging path. Three types of transducers were made based on a stacked design, in two different sizes. The optical windows were 20-mm and 10-mm with outer diameters of 50-mm and 38-mm respectively. The devices were characterised for acoustic bandwidth and sensitivity using a pulse receive technique. The acoustic power was measured using a custom made radiation force balance. The beam profile was measured using a three-dimensional scanning chamber with a mobile needle-hydrophone. The transient response waveform of a burst wave was captured using the needle hydrophone, and an FFT was performed to get the power spectrum to determine the linearity of the ultrasound generation of the transducer. The frequency response showed that these transducers had a large FWHM bandwidth of 56%. The field scans showed that the acoustic propagation pattern was very similar to traditional ultrasound transducers, yet the different constructions affected the focal distance and sidelobes. In addition surface scans, indicated that in all transducers glass window acted like an oscillating diaphragm generating ultrasound. The acoustic power measurements indicated that these devices could exceed acoustic powers of 16 W. Traditional ultrasonic imaging only requires several milliwatts whereas therapeutic application only require several watts. These transducers indicate their potential for multimodal imaging and therapy for example combining endoscopy with ultrasound surgery, or simultaneous ultrasound and bioluminescence imaging.